

Land Accumulation and Concentration for the Development of High-Tech Agriculture in Hanoi City, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT

Encouraging land accumulation and concentration in agriculture has been one of the key policies implemented by Hanoi City in recent years to foster the development of high-tech agriculture in the city. By synthesizing secondary data and relevant sources, this paper seeks to assess the current situation of agricultural land accumulation and concentration for high-tech agricultural development in Hanoi, identify the existing challenges associated with different forms of land accumulation and concentration, and propose several solutions to promote more effective land consolidation in support of high-tech agriculture in the coming period.

Keywords: High technology, agriculture, land accumulation and concentration, Hanoi City

INTRODUCTION

The application of high technology in agricultural production is regarded as an approach to sustainable agricultural development, helping to address challenges in the sector through the superior advantages of modern technologies such as greenhouse technology, automation, and sensor technology. These applications contribute to cost savings, productivity improvement, reduction of production costs, enhancement of product quality, and environmental protection, while also reducing the dependence of agricultural production on natural factors such as weather and climate (Zhang et al., 2010). Consequently, the development of high-tech agriculture has become a dominant trend and a key driver of success in countries with advanced agricultural sectors, and it is also considered an inevitable direction for Vietnam's agriculture in the integration era (Tran Duc Vien, 2017; Pham Van Hien, 2014), particularly under the profound influence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. In recent years, the development of high-tech agriculture has been vigorously promoted in many localities across the country, yielding notable achievements. Hanoi, the capital of Vietnam, serves as the country's socio-economic development hub. Nevertheless, the

city still retains a substantial agricultural land area of 195.8 thousand hectares (accounting for 58.3% of its total natural land area), with the rural population making up around 50% and agricultural labor representing 40.2% of the city's total workforce (Hoang Nam, 2021). To ensure food security and safety, enhance the value and competitiveness of agricultural products, and increase farmers' income, the promotion of high-tech agriculture has become an inevitable trend—particularly in the context of shrinking cultivated land and the growing impacts of both climate change and the Fourth Industrial Revolution on agricultural production. In recent years, Hanoi has introduced a number of policies to promote the application of high-tech agriculture. However, the outcomes remain relatively modest. By 2021, the city had established only 164 high-tech agricultural models, with high-tech agriculture contributing approximately 25% of the total agricultural production value. Among the key factors hindering the adoption of high technology in agricultural production, fragmented landholdings have been identified as a major barrier (Do Minh, 2019; Quang Phu, 2019). Therefore, fostering land accumulation and concentration is deemed essential to accelerate the adoption of high-tech agriculture in Hanoi. Based on secondary data collected from

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various sources, this paper aims to assess the current situation and propose solutions to enhance land accumulation and concentration for the development of high-tech agriculture in the city in the coming years.

METHODOLOGY

This study primarily relies on secondary data collected from reports of the Hanoi Party Committee, the Hanoi People’s Committee, as well as findings from previously published research. In addition, the study conducted in-depth interviews with experts and managers from the Hanoi Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, the Central Committee of the Vietnam Farmers’ Union, along with focus group discussions involving business owners, agricultural cooperatives, and farming households applying high technology in agricultural production in the city. These activities aimed to gather assessments of the difficulties in land accumulation and concentration for high-tech agricultural development and to elicit proposed solutions to overcome them. The research

also employed inherited research methods, descriptive statistical analysis, comparative analysis, and synthesis as the main methodological approaches.

STUDY RESULTS

3.1. The Development of High-Tech Agriculture in Hanoi

In order to promote the development of high-tech agriculture, Hanoi City issued Resolution No. 03/2015/NQ-HĐND dated July 8, 2015, of the Hanoi People’s Council on several policies for implementing the High-Tech Agricultural Development Program in Hanoi for the period 2016–2020. Subsequently, Decision No. 28/2017/QĐ-UBND dated August 7, 2017, of the Hanoi People’s Committee was promulgated to provide guidance on the implementation of Resolution No. 03/2015/NQ-HĐND concerning policies to support the development of high-tech agriculture in Hanoi during 2016–2020 (see Table 1).

Table 1. Selected Policies to Promote the Development of High-Tech Agriculture in Hanoi

Policy Document	Main content
1. Resolution No. 03/2015/NQ-HĐND dated July 8, 2015	Issuing several policies to implement the High-Tech Agricultural Development Program in Hanoi for the period 2016–2020.
2. Resolution No. 10/2018/NQ-HĐND dated December 5, 2018	Issuing several policies to encourage production development, promote cooperation and linkages in agricultural production and product consumption, and improve rural infrastructure in Hanoi.
3. Decision No. 1170/2015/QĐ-UBND dated December 24, 2015	Approving the High-Tech Agricultural Development Program of Hanoi for the period 2016–2020.
4. Decision No. 28/2017/QĐ-UBND dated August 7, 2017	Providing guidance on the implementation of Resolution No. 03/2015/NQ-HĐND dated July 8, 2015 of the Hanoi People’s Council.
5. Decision No. 437/2019/QĐ-UBND dated January 21, 2019	Approving the plan for restructuring Hanoi’s agricultural sector for the period 2019–2020.
5. Decision No. 3215/2019/QĐ-UBND dated June 14, 2019	Issuing the list of specialized agricultural production zones and criteria for high-tech agricultural production in Hanoi.

(Source: Compiled by the authors)

Hanoi has carried out the planning of concentrated high-tech agricultural production zones across its

districts. By 2020, the city had planned nine high-tech agricultural production zones with a total area of 1,628.6 hectares (Table 2).

Table 2. Planned Development of High-Tech Agricultural Zones in Hanoi

Location	Area (ha)
1. High-Tech Agricultural Zone in Dong Anh District	96,6
2. High-Tech Agricultural Zone in Hoai Duc District (An Thuong and Song Phuong Communes)	668
3. High-Tech Agricultural Zone in Ha Dong District (Yen Nghia Ward)	76
4. High-Tech Agricultural Zone in Me Linh District (Hoang Kim Commune)	105
5. High-Tech Agricultural Zone in Dan Phuong District (Song Phuong and Dong Thap Communes)	33
6. High-Tech Agricultural Zone in Phuc Tho District (Hiep Thuan Commune)	200
7. High-Tech Agricultural Zone in Son Tay Town (Kim Son Commune)	80
8. High-Tech Agricultural Zone in Soc Son District (Thanh Son and Tan Dan Communes)	70
9. High-Tech Agricultural Zone in Ba Vi District	300
Total	1628,6

(Source: Nguyen Xuan Dinh & Nguyen Mau Dung, 2021)

By 2021, Hanoi had implemented 164 high-tech agricultural models. In crop production, nearly 130 hectares of vegetables were cultivated using net houses, and about 50 hectares applied water-saving irrigation technologies. Floriculture had initially adopted high-tech applications in certain stages, such as building greenhouses and net houses, installing air conditioners and devices to regulate temperature and light, and applying water-saving irrigation. More than 1,000 hectares of fruit production also applied high-tech methods. In livestock farming, 30% of large-scale pig and poultry farms used closed housing

systems, along with 87% of dairy farms and over 50% of beef cattle farms. More than 75% of dairy farms, 44% of beef cattle farms, and 44% of large-scale pig farms located outside residential areas had adopted biogas digesters. Meanwhile, 65% of dairy farms, 45% of beef cattle farms, 85% of pig farms, and 85% of poultry farms applied biological products for environmental treatment in livestock production (Nguyen Xuan Dinh & Nguyen Mau Dung, 2021). In aquaculture, producers had applied high technology in several aspects, such as oxygen enrichment using paddle-wheel aerators, the use of biological products for water environment treatment, and the adoption of Biofloc technology.

Table 3. Number of High-Tech Agricultural Models in Hanoi in 2022

Sectors	Number of models	Percentage (%)
1. Crop production	109	66,5
2. Livestock	40	24,4
3. Aquaculture	15	9,1
Total	164	100,0

(Source: Nguyen Xuan Dinh & Nguyen Mau Dung, 2021)

High-tech agricultural models have been established in all 18 districts and towns of Hanoi where agricultural production is practiced. Districts with the highest number of models include Me Linh (19 models), Gia Lam (19), Thuong Tin (16), Dong Anh (12), and Thanh Oai (11). Although the number of high-tech agricultural models in the city has been steadily increasing year by year, most models have only applied high technology to certain stages of production. At present, there is only one model in the

city that applies high technology across the entire production process—namely, the enoki mushroom production model using a Japanese high-tech production line developed by Thanh Cao Kinoko Import-Export Co., Ltd. in My Duc District. To date, the application of high technology in agricultural production has contributed about 30% of Hanoi’s total agricultural output value. High-tech models have achieved yields 10–12% higher than traditional production methods and increased economic efficiency by 25–28% (Doan Thi Thu Huong, 2021). Nevertheless, in general, the development of high-tech agriculture in Hanoi has mainly focused on

specific stages rather than comprehensive application, resulting in limited stability, insufficient sustainability, and significant economic benefits only for a small number of enterprises, cooperatives, and farming households.

3.2. Current Situation of Land Accumulation and Concentration for High-Tech Agricultural Development in Hanoi

3.2.1. Land Consolidation and Concentration in Hanoi

Land accumulation refers to the act in which landowners and land users employ various measures such as purchase, transfer, or other means to increase the scale of landholdings they own and use. **Land concentration**, on the other hand, is understood as the process of enlarging land areas for production, business, or other purposes without changing the ownership or land-use rights of the landowners or land users (Do Kim Chung, 2018). Accordingly, agricultural land accumulation can be understood as the increase in the land area of a land user through the acquisition of land-use rights, while agricultural land concentration refers to the expansion of agricultural land area through transactions that do not alter the land-use rights of land users. The processes of agricultural land accumulation and concentration are carried out through the following methods: (1) Land consolidation and plot exchange (dồn điền, đổi thửa); (2) Leasing of agricultural land-use rights; (3) Linkages and cooperation in agricultural production; (4) Contributing capital with agricultural land-use rights; (5) Transferring agricultural land-use rights. Hanoi has identified **land consolidation and parcel exchange** as a breakthrough solution to implement Program No. 02-CTr/TU of the Municipal Party Committee on *Agricultural development, new rural*

construction, and improvement of farmers' livelihoods. To achieve this objective, the city has promulgated a number of concrete plans and policies, notably Plan No. 171/KH-UBND (2013) and Program No. 02-CTr/TU dated April 26, 2016 on agricultural development for the period 2016–2020. Within these frameworks, the review, supplementation, and improvement of mechanisms and policies encouraging enterprises and farmers to consolidate and exchange land plots and invest in agricultural production were considered key solutions. In addition, the Hanoi People's Council issued Resolution No. 10/2018/NQ-HĐND, which stipulates a set of incentives for land consolidation and parcel exchange. Accordingly, the Hanoi municipal government will provide **full financial support** for land surveying, re-issuance of land use right certificates, mapping, field planning, and the construction of in-field transportation and irrigation systems in accordance with state technical norms. Financial support will also be provided for commune- and village-level steering committees to cover operational costs, meetings, and communication activities. The support level is **1,000,000 VND per hectare**, funded entirely by the municipal budget. For expenses related to the excavation and construction of in-field transportation and irrigation systems after land consolidation and parcel exchange, the city will subsidize **70% of total costs**, in which the municipal budget contributes **50%** (allocated as targeted transfers to district budgets), and district budgets contribute **20%**. Furthermore, the city will provide **full financial support for the procurement of input materials** (calculated according to state technical norms) used for the solidification of in-field roads and irrigation systems. Of this amount, the municipal budget covers **80%** (through targeted transfers to district budgets), while district budgets cover **20%**.

Table 4. Results of Land Consolidation and Issuance of Land Use Right Certificates in Hanoi

STT	District	Plan for Land Consolidation and Exchange (ha)	Result for Land Consolidation and Exchange (ha)	Result/plan (%)	Number of Land Use Right Certificates to be Issued	Rate of Issued Land Use Right Certificates (%)
1	Ba Vi	4652,0	5735	123,3	40022	100,0
2	Ung Hoa	5602,8	6534	116,6	159422	100,0
3	Son Tay	1004,5	1078	107,4	6884	100,0
4	Soc Son	10126,2	10845	107,1	31924	100,0
5	Thuong Tin	4302,2	4546	105,7	24288	100,0
6	Phu Xuyen	8607,4	9060	105,3	45396	98,9

7	Thach That	2100,2	2172	103,4	12539	100,0
8	Thanh Oai	5102,5	5175,6	101,4	32072	97,6
9	Chuong Mai	10443,5	10522	100,8	45558	96,5
10	Phuc Tho	3685,1	3708	100,6	25534	100,0
11	Me Linh	3280,0	3280	100,0	16230	95,6
12	Quoc Oai	4350,1	4350	100,0	44173	100
13	Thanh Tri	816,9	817	100,0	8488	100
14	Dan Phuong	16,9	16,9	100,0	71339	99,3
15	My Duc	7513,9	7486	99,6	39025	99,3
16	Dong Anh	1994,5	1865	93,5	10731	96,8
17	Gia Lam	1461,0	1343	91,9	7220	97,4
18	Hoai Duc	920,5	921	100,0	2116	100,0
	Total	75980,1	79454,3	100,6	622861	99,2

(Source: Hanoi Party Committee, 2020).

As of June 2020, Hanoi had completed land consolidation and plot exchange for 79,454.3 hectares, achieving 104.6% of the planned target (Hanoi Party Committee, 2020). Following land consolidation, the city had also essentially completed the issuance of agricultural land use right certificates to farming households, with 617,964 certificates issued, reaching 99.2% of the target. Only three localities had yet to complete the land consolidation plan, namely Dong Anh district (129.1 ha), Gia Lam district (117.8 ha), and My Duc district (27.9 ha). Through the land consolidation program, the city converted 40,229.4 hectares from rice and vegetable cultivation into more economically efficient production models. At present, Hanoi has established several specialized agricultural production zones, such as flower-growing areas in Me Linh and Dan Phuong districts, fruit cultivation areas in Chuong My and Hoai Duc districts, and concentrated livestock farming zones in Ba Vi, Ung Hoa, and Quoc Oai districts.

2.2.2. Forms of Agricultural Land Accumulation and Concentration for High-Tech Agricultural Development in Hanoi and Emerging Issues

Among the total number of high-tech agricultural (HTA) models in Hanoi, household and farm-based models account for the largest proportion, while models established by enterprises and companies applying high-tech agriculture represent only about 12% of the total. Notably, only one company has been recognized by the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, namely Kinoko Thanh Cao Import-

Export Co., Ltd. As of the end of 2020, Hanoi had 50 agricultural cooperatives applying high-tech agriculture out of a total of 1,090 active agricultural cooperatives (Son Hà, 2021). The main forms of agricultural land accumulation and concentration for high-tech agricultural development in Hanoi currently include:

- (1) Households exchange the locations of their plots with one another in order to reduce the number of fragmented plots and increase the size of each household’s landholding (with or without monetary compensation for differences in proximity or land quality). This process is usually supported and facilitated by cooperatives as well as village and commune authorities. However, it is very difficult to accumulate large areas of land in this way, as it requires negotiations and agreements with multiple households. In many cases, such exchanges are only based on verbal agreements or handwritten notes, which lack strong legal validity. Consequently, when a household refuses to continue the exchange for various reasons, households or farms applying high-tech agriculture face considerable difficulties.
- (2) Households lease, purchase, or receive transfers of land use rights from other households in order to expand production, thereby becoming farms or large-scale households. The rental price, contract duration, and payment methods are determined by mutual agreement between the parties. However, certain constraints remain, such as the legal limit on the transfer of land use rights for annual crops and aquaculture land, which may not exceed ten times the allocation quota. In many cases, land lease or purchase agreements between households are only

recorded through handwritten contracts, sometimes with neighboring households acting as witnesses, resulting in weak legal validity. When a household refuses to continue leasing, farms face significant difficulties. Furthermore, this arrangement may also give rise to speculative behavior, whereby agricultural land is accumulated in anticipation of conversion to non-agricultural purposes.

(3) Households contribute their land to agricultural cooperatives or collaborative groups: In certain localities, households have voluntarily joined together to establish collaborative groups or agricultural cooperatives applying high-tech agriculture. While participating in these organizations, households continue cultivating their own land, but under the coordination and guidance of the cooperative or group. When cooperatives or collaborative groups perform their functions effectively, they can provide substantial support to member households. However, if these organizations suffer from poor physical infrastructure, insufficient operating capital, limited managerial capacity, lack of government support, and a narrow scope or low effectiveness of activities, their ability to support member households will be constrained and ineffective.

(4) Enterprises lease land from farming households or purchase and acquire land use rights from households for production purposes: The major obstacle for enterprises is the need to mobilize and negotiate with each household individually. When a large tract of land is required, enterprises must negotiate with hundreds or even thousands of households. Although in many localities enterprises have received support and assistance from village and commune authorities as well as cooperatives, the process remains highly challenging. In some cases, local authorities such as commune People's Committees or cooperatives have leased land from farmers and subsequently re-leased it to enterprises (e.g., in Đan Phượng District). Moreover, under current legal regulations, enterprises are only permitted to sign land lease contracts for a maximum period of five years—a duration that is far too short for long-term investment.

(5) Households contribute land by converting its value into shares of an enterprise, thereby becoming both shareholders and laborers within the enterprise.

In theory, farmers participate as shareholders by contributing land, while enterprises invest in infrastructure, transfer technology, and secure product consumption. Profits are distributed according to the shareholders' capital contribution and labor input. This arrangement strengthens the linkage between households and enterprises by aligning their interests, while enterprises reduce costs associated with leasing or purchasing land use rights. However, this form also presents challenges and risks for households. For instance, if enterprises cultivate perennial industrial crops, there may be no income or dividends distributed during the initial years. In cases where enterprises incur losses, households may not only forgo income but also risk losing their contributed capital (i.e., their land). Additionally, enterprises may face risks stemming from arbitrary contract breaches by participating households.

3.3. Solutions to Promote Agricultural Land Accumulation and Concentration for High-Tech Agriculture Development in Hanoi

The accumulation and concentration of agricultural land are both a prerequisite and a necessary condition for the development of high-tech agriculture, thereby enhancing productivity, improving product quality, and increasing land-use efficiency in Hanoi as well as in other localities nationwide. In addition to recommending that the Government develop and finalize mechanisms and policies on land accumulation and concentration (including the prompt adoption of a decree on agricultural land accumulation and concentration for production, following consultations with relevant agencies, organizations, and individuals on the draft decree), which would serve as an important foundation for localities to systematically and consistently implement agricultural land accumulation and concentration, a number of measures should be undertaken to promote land consolidation and concentration for the development of high-tech agriculture in Hanoi, as follows:

- The city should strengthen communication and awareness-raising efforts to enhance public understanding of the necessity of land accumulation and concentration for the formation of specialized agricultural production zones and high-tech agricultural areas. In addition, it is essential to clearly

explain the rights, obligations, and responsibilities of farming households, cooperatives, and enterprises under each form of land accumulation and concentration. This will help build consensus during the process of land consolidation and concentration to serve the development of high-tech agriculture.

- It is necessary to ensure that the process of land accumulation and concentration is conducted transparently, democratically, and in accordance with market mechanisms, while safeguarding the rights of farmers as well as the interests of enterprises. According to Nguyen Quang Thuan (2020), empirical research indicates that amending restrictive regulations (such as landholding limits or lease terms) is often less important than building “trust” among farmers and enterprises through clear regulations on land-use and transfer rights, particularly in rural contexts. In resolving land-related conflicts and disputes, it is essential to ensure the participation of all relevant stakeholders, accompanied by oversight and management from community-based organizations.

- Review land-use planning to ensure that plans remain stable and are oriented toward the long term, meeting the requirements of agricultural sector restructuring, with priority given to the development of high-tech agriculture. In addition, it is necessary to publicly disclose approved land-use plans authorized by competent state agencies, thereby facilitating access for land users and enterprises investing in agriculture, enabling them to easily obtain information and feel assured when investing in the development of high-tech agriculture.

- Link the process of farmland accumulation and concentration with the restructuring of the economy and the reallocation of rural labor. At the same time, encourage the development of cooperative models and attract enterprises to invest in large-scale high-tech agriculture.

- Strengthen research, transfer, and application of science and technology in production, processing, and business activities; replicate successful production and business models; and enhance linkages in production and product consumption to establish high-tech agricultural value chains, thereby ensuring stability and sustainability in the development of

high-tech agriculture in the city. To improve the efficiency of cooperation among land users in concentrating farmland for large-scale production, it is necessary to encourage contractual arrangements between farmers and enterprises or cooperatives. Such contracts should clearly specify the rights and responsibilities of both parties in a balanced manner, as well as include provisions for handling violations. The intermediary role of state agencies in facilitating and strengthening these linkages should also be further promoted.

CONCLUSION

In the context of declining cultivated land area and the strong impact of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, in recent years, Hanoi has issued numerous policies to promote the development of high-tech agriculture in order to ensure food security and safety, enhance the value and competitiveness of agricultural products, and improve the efficiency of agricultural land use in the city. Among these, the encouragement of farmland accumulation and concentration has been given special attention. By 2020, the city had completed land consolidation for 79,454.3 hectares, reaching 104.6% of the plan, and had essentially finished issuing agricultural land use right certificates to farming households. On this basis, the city has planned nine high-tech agricultural zones with a total area of 1,628.6 hectares, and up to now, there are 164 high-tech agricultural application models operating across the city. The main forms of farmland accumulation and concentration for high-tech agricultural development include land exchange among households, leasing and purchasing land-use rights from households, and contributing land to cooperatives, agricultural cooperatives, or enterprises applying high-tech agriculture. Solutions to promote farmland accumulation and concentration for high-tech agricultural development in Hanoi include strengthening communication and raising public awareness about land accumulation and concentration; ensuring that the process takes place transparently, democratically, and in line with market mechanisms; reviewing agricultural land-use planning to ensure long-term stability and making it publicly accessible; linking farmland accumulation and concentration with economic restructuring and rural labor reallocation; and strengthening the

application of science and technology in production as well as in product consumption linkages.

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